

SPECIAL ISSUE: Spatial Transformation from a Planning Perspective

Exploring leverage points for a transformation-fit regional planning in Lower-Saxony

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Abstract

German spatial research argues that regional planning could play a pivotal role in shaping the socio-ecological transformation. In reality, regional planning in Germany is struggling to maintain its significance as it is increasingly being replaced by supposedly quick and easy sectoral solutions. A central regional planning issue is its lack of adaptability. Despite numerous ideas for more flexible, informal regional governance, planning practice remains stuck in its formal paradigm. This article uses a leverage point perspective (LPP) to identify practical challenges, adaptation strategies and implementation obstacles in western Lower Saxony. The case study centres on a stakeholder workshop, which was supplemented by surveys and document analysis. The key findings show that capacity constraints and an unclear socio-political mandate limit regional planning to a weak role characterised by formal requirements. There seems to be support for a more strategic and communication-focused shift, but a streamlining of formal practices was deemed a precondition. A shift must also aim to strengthen the societal basis for actions. The LPP offers a concise overview for intervention possibilities and can serve as a preliminary step for the necessary socio-political process to determine the actual adaptation strategy.

Keywords

Regional planning;
leverage point
perspective;
transformation;
Lower Saxony

Introduction

Our society is facing a polycrisis, which demands a transformation towards a sustainable, post-fossil economy. In 2011, the German Advisory Council on Global Change proposed the concept of a “proactive state” as a means of facilitating socio-ecological transformation (WBGU, 2011). Hofmeister et al. (2021) suggest that at least in theory the spatial planning system should be predestined to play a pivotal role in the implementation of the “proactive state”. Firmly grounded in a robust legal framework, German spatial planning offers a well-established variety of regulatory, strategic, and communicative instruments at all levels of government to facilitate

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the socio-ecological transformation (cf. Hofmeister et al., 2021). As such, regional planning seems destined to be a central facilitator by connecting overarching policies and local initiatives. Key issues of the transition, such as energy and mobility, require supra-local solutions, which should ideally be handled at regional level (Hahn et al., 2022; Purkarthofer, 2020).

However, despite these good reasons, the actual impact of regional planning on transformation in Germany seems neglectable (Hofmeister & Warner, 2021; Lamker & Levin-Keitel, 2019; Hahn et al., 2022; Heuer, Schäfer, & Schaal, 2024). Even worse, regional planning seems to be increasingly pushed into the background despite growing demands (Smas & Schmitt, 2021). In an age of great acceleration, holistic planning is coming under increasing pressure of imminent sectoral requirements. In German federal politics, this can be seen, for example, in the introduction of overriding interests (§2 EEG) and fixed spatial targets for sectoral requirements (§1 WindBG) (Grotefels & Priebs, 2024; Scholz, 2023). These interventions in the competences of regional planning highlight the pressure for change and challenges regional planning particularly, as it has not progressed in its aspired direction for decades (Hahn et al., 2022; Sondermann & Maikämper, 2024). Sondermann und Maikämper (2024) have shown that since 1980, German planning scholars have supported a shift towards a stronger regional perspective, more flexibility, new implementation-oriented instruments and process acceleration by favouring lean plans. However, these ideas had only a minor impact on actual planning practice. More informal practices have emerged (Brockhagen et al., 2023) but without replacing formal planning task (Eichhorn et al., 2023). In comparison to other European countries, the German planning system proves steady and almost unchanged (Münter & Reimer, 2023; Nadin et al., 2021). While this robustness could be seen as a strength in the past (Smas & Schmitt, 2021), the question arises as to whether this inertia now poses a barrier for necessary adjustments. Due to increasing challenges, there can be no doubt that regional planning practice must adapt to the requirements of transformation (Birkmann et al., 2011; Hofmeister & Warner, 2022).

This article utilises a leverage points perspective (LPP) to examine the possibilities for intervention to enhance regional planning practice within its systemic structures. The LPP represents an analytical framework that has been established in the field of sustainability research as a means of identifying potential intervention options within complex systems. Its key benefit is the combination of causal problem analysis with teleological goal identification (Abson et al., 2017; Fischer et al., 2022; Meadows, 1999). The LPP has been selected as a means of connecting the pursuit of idealistic solutions with the consideration of practical constraints. The objective of this article is to study the implementation gap of regional planning through a concise example. The LPP was chosen as a transformative approach to actively initiate a necessary

debate on the need for improvements in regional planning in Weser-Ems in Lower Saxony, Germany. Potential leverage points were determined from discussions and surveys with regional planning stakeholders and enhanced by planning literature, and their systematic connections and current constraints were analysed.

Regional planning in Weser-Ems was chosen because of its distinctive, small-scale approach of municipalised regional planning that has been criticised in terms of its effectiveness since its introduction in the 1970s and has not shown considerable improvement since (cf. Bogumil & Ebinger, 2019; Bogumil et al., 2018; Fürst, 1987; Gnest, 2008; Heuer, Schäfer, & Schaal, 2024; Pehlke et al., 2021; Spiekermann & Franck, 2014). In particular, the organisation of urban-rural relationships remains an unsolved problem in Weser-Ems due to the separation of regional planning competences of the large cities from the surrounding rural areas. The lack of adaptation is particularly apparent, as other regions in Lower Saxony have exhibited ways of adapting regional planning to current challenges. Furthermore, Weser-Ems was chosen because it is particularly affected by the socio-ecological transformation in terms of energy transition and adapting land-use practices.

Research Design

The objective of the case study is the identification of leverage points for adapting regional planning practices in Weser-Ems towards the socio-ecological transformation. Current constraints and their causes are discussed and opportunities and obstacles of different leverage points are identified. The article centres on three research questions:

- Which leverage points have stakeholders in the case study region identified to address the structural deficiencies of regional planning and strengthen its role in facilitating socio-ecological transformation?
- To what extent do the leverage points identified by stakeholders align with those discussed in literature on regional planning and transformation?
- What specific advantages does the application of the leverage points perspective offer for fostering co-creative problem-solving in the revision of regional planning practices?

The focus is on governmental actions, following a narrow understanding of regional planning practices (Levin-Keitel & Behrend, 2022). A normative perspective on socio-ecological transformation, as conceptualised by the German Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU, 2011) is applied. This socio-ecological transformation is regarded as an indispensable shift towards a sustainable, post-fossil society. This shift is viewed as a cultural project that must be initiated and coordinated by a “proactive state” (WBGU, 2011; Schneidewind, 2018).

Methods

A multi-method approach comprising document analysis of the principal planning documents, a stakeholder workshop, and a survey on planning structures has been employed (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Multi-method approach (own visualisation)

The initial phase of the case study entailed an examination of the utilisation of extant regional planning documents. Regional plans were emphasised as they constitute the primary instrument of regional planning (Priebes, 2019). An examination was conducted of the contents and regulations of all valid regional plans (*Regionale Raumordnungsprogramme*) in the research area. In a subsequent step, an analysis was conducted into the regulations that had been adopted from the state level¹, those that had been adopted by the local level², and which regulations had been considered in concepts on regional funding³.

In light of the findings, a stakeholder workshop was held with the aim of addressing the prevailing challenges in regional planning in shaping the transformation in Weser-Ems. The

¹ By examining all relevant versions of the state regional plan (*Landes-Raumordnungsprogramm*).

² By examining a convenience selection of land-use plans from 25 municipalities from 4 counties. The convenience selection followed the “most different case design” by Baur and Christmann (2021). It aimed to provide a cross-section of the various counties, as well as the different ages of regional plans.

³ The regional funding concepts of LEADER, “Zukunftsregionen” and the “Metropolregion Nordwest” were considered. Regarding the LEADER concept a convenience selection was used following the “most different case design” by Baur and Christmann (2021) to select 6 different LEADER regions.

workshop was attended by 40 regional planning stakeholders from the case study region and the neighbouring Dutch province of Groningen. The participants were divided into three working groups to discuss “future priorities”, “future instruments” and “future of participation”. The implementation of a closed group division was necessitated in order to ensure that the diverse stakeholder groups were represented in the working groups in a balanced manner. The results of a self-completion questionnaire among the participants, using an audience response system, formed the basis for the group discussions. The participants' beliefs regarding their role as planners were investigated through the use of Likert-type scales, forced distribution, multiple-choice and open response questions.

The workshop's findings highlighted the necessity for further investigation into the structures and financial resources associated with regional planning. In a supplementary survey, the regional planning agencies in the case study region were invited to complete a self-completion questionnaire regarding their internal structures, number of positions, salaries, and vacancies. The findings were systematically analysed using a leverage points perspective.

Leverage points perspective (LPP)

The LPP is an analytical framework to systematise places to intervene in a system. 12 so-called leverage points were determined by Meadows (1999) and refined by Abson et al. (2017), and grouped according to their system characteristics (realms) (see Table 1). The leverage points related to intent and design are perceived as more powerful “deep leverages”. These deep leverages should gain more attention, as decision makers usually focus more on “shallow leverages” regarding feedbacks and parameter. The *intent* of a system describes its purpose and its fundamental orientation. The *design* realm considers the implementation of the system's intent, which is expressed through the organisation of its components, the rules that govern their interactions, and the information flows that connect them. The *feedbacks* can be defined as a description of the impact of an action within a system and the *parameter* of a system represents the practical implementation (Abson et al., 2017).

The LPP establishes a hierarchy of interventions (Abson et al., 2017; Fischer et al., 2022). In the process of identifying appropriate interventions, the objective is to ascertain the combination of leverages that offers the greatest efficiency (Bolton, 2022; Fischer et al., 2022; Rosengren et al., 2020). The leverages are interconnected in complex ways and the deepest leverages are not by default the most appropriate (Abson et al., 2017; Meadows, 1999). Addressing one leverage can result in unintended butterfly effects (Bolton, 2022). It is therefore recommended that the focus should be placed on addressing the leverages in their overall systemic context (Abson et al., 2017; Angheloiu & Tennant, 2020; Bolton, 2022; Meadows, 1999). In some cases, it may be

necessary to take an intervention detour to circumvent controversial or unchangeable systemic issues (Fischer et al., 2022). The LPP aims to determine which individual aspects to examine more comprehensively (Bolton, 2022; Fischer et al., 2022; Meadows, 1999; Rosengren et al., 2020). It has been demonstrated to be particularly effective for integrating causal problem analysis with teleological goal identification (Abson et al., 2017; Angheloiu & Tennant, 2020; Riechers et al., 2022; Riechers et al., 2021; Rosengren et al., 2020).

Table 1 - Leverage points perspective according to Abson et al. (2017).

Realm	Leverage point	Description
Intent	1. Transcending paradigms	The power to transcend paradigms.
	2. Paradigms	The mind-set out of which the system – its goals, structure, rules, delays, parameters – arises.
	3. Goals	The purpose or function of the system.
Design	4. Self-organisation	The power to add, change, or evolve system structure.
	5. Rules	Incentives, punishments, constraints.
	6. Information flows	The structure of who does and does not have access to information.
Feedbacks	7. Reinforcing feedback loops	The strength of the gain of driving loops.
	8. Balancing feedback loops	The strengths of the feedbacks relative to the impacts they are trying to correct.
	9. Delays	The lengths of time relative to the rates of system changes.
Parameter	10. Stock and flow structures	Physical systems and their nodes of intersection.
	11. Buffers	The sizes of stabilising stocks relatives to their flows.
	12. Numbers	Constants and parameters such as subsidies, taxes, standards.

As outlined by Abson et al. (2017) the LPP comprises the principal steps of:

- 1) identifying the levels of intervention (what are the know system characteristics that can be address? e.g. how are competences of planning organised (4. Self-organisation),
- 2) identifying the leverages of intervention (what measures can be taken? e.g. strengthening the regional level competences) and
- 3) exploring the interconnections between the leverages (how do measures influence other system characteristics? e.g. strengthening the regional level is dependant on a “2. Paradigm” that favours a regional solution as well as “10. Stocks” and “11. Buffers” that allow for its implementation).

The results of these steps in relation to the case study are presented in Section 4 and discussed in Section 5.

Selection of the case study

A case study design was selected due to the multitude of existing planning practices in Germany (Wiechmann, 2019b) and due to the impact planning culture has on planning practices (Sondermann, 2017). A single case study allows for a more detailed examination of the case's complexity. The application of the LPP aims to gain broader value beyond the case study itself (Bryman, 2012; Yin 2018).

Weser-Ems was selected due to its particular small-scale regional planning authorities⁴, which provide an illustrative example of the municipalised regional planning approach implemented by Lower Saxony (Bogumil, 2019). The term 'Weser-Ems' refers to the area of responsibility of the 'Weser-Ems Regional Development Agency'⁵, which corresponds to the EU NUTS2 level DE94 (Honé, 2014). However, the responsibility for regional planning lies with the 12 county and 5 county-free cities within Weser-Ems (see Figure 2). Despite long known issues of this small-scale approach no reform or formalised adaptation measures have been implemented in Weser-Ems so far (Bogumil et al., 2018; Fürst, 1987; Heuer et. al. 2024).

Specific spatial challenges in Weser-Ems exist in terms of its relatively rural-peripheral character, which affects the access to services of general interest negatively and has led to above-average car-dependency (Küpper & Milbert, 2023, Thünen Institut, 2024). Weser-Ems is undergoing structural changes in terms of energy by adapting its existing infrastructure for storing and transporting fossil fuels to hydrogen usage (Schüpp & Kühne, 2020, Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Umwelt, Energie und Klimaschutz, 2024). The region is the primary bottleneck for the transportation of offshore wind energy and gas energy (Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Umwelt, Energie und Klimaschutz, 2024) and the majority of grid expansion directly impacts the region (Bundesnetzagentur, 2022). Other major planning challenges exist regarding the protection of peatlands as carbon reservoirs and the transformation of agriculture. The region is home to the highest concentration of moorlands in Germany (Hauck-Bramsiepe et al., 2022) and

⁴ In comparison to the 17 regional planning authorities in Weser-Ems, the neighbouring region Münster in North Rhine-Westphalia (NUTS2 DEA3) is managed by a single regional planning authority (BBSR, 2024). The regions have a comparable number of inhabitants (Weser-Ems 2,592,162; Münster 2,664,280) but vary in area (Weser-Ems 14,987 km², Münster 6,918 km²) (BBSR, 2024).

⁵ The Weser-Ems Regional Development Agency is a state-level agency. It serves as a regional point of contact for the provision of advice on matters pertaining to regional planning and regional development. The primary responsibilities of the agency include the provision of guidance on financial assistance programmes and the facilitation of interregional developments and projects, such as the issuance of spatial planning permits for major infrastructure initiatives. Despite its role as the authorising body for regional planning authorities, the agency lacks direct formal power in regional planning (Bogumil et al. (2018); Honé (2014)).

the core region of industrial agriculture and animal husbandry in Germany (Dannenberg, 2020). This has led to a complex interplay of spatial conflicts, where the conservation of land is juxtaposed with the competing demands of peat extraction and agricultural use (Schmatzler, 2015).

Figure 2 - Case study area Weser-Ems (own visualisation)

Background: A transformation-fit regional planning for Lower Saxony

Regional planning practice in Weser-Ems

The German planning system is founded upon a federalist, multi-level governance structure. The legal principle of subsidiarity ensures that each decision should be taking on the lowest possible level, ensuring a municipal planning sovereignty. The mutual feedback principle ensures a constant countervailing influence between each level of planning. The most significant formal legal plans are the binding land use plan (*Bebauungsplan*) und preparatory land use plan (*Flächennutzungsplan*) at the local level, the regional plans (*Regionales Raumordnungsprogramm*) at the regional level, and the state regional plans (*Landes-Raumordnungsprogramm*) at the state level (Bogumil, 2019; Danielzyk & Münter, 2019).

The main objective of regional planning is seen in the interdisciplinary, integrative coordination of land use interests (Fürst and Mäding, 2011). Its main formal task consists of the mandatory tasks of preparing regional plans, issuing regional planning procedures (*Raumordnungsverfahren*) and drafting statements to other authorities regarding their plans. In addition, regional planning authorities may initiate voluntary informal tasks such as moderating regional stakeholder networks, drafting regional development concepts or managing funds (Priebes, 2019; Wiechmann, 2008).

The design of regional planning is subject to significant variation between states. Lower Saxony is unique in using a municipalised regional planning approach (Eichhorn & Pehlke, 2022; Priebes, 2023). This approach is reflective of the historically robust political role of the local level in Lower Saxony. Moreover, it is a consequence of the rejection of planning control by the state, which was perceived as unduly restrictive in the decades prior the reform in the 1970s. The establishment of municipalised regional planning is impeded by the fact that the parallel territorial reform failed to establish the anticipated large counties (Fürst, 1987; Gnest, 2008). As a result, regional planning in Lower Saxony is characterised by a lack of comprehensive coverage, limited staffing resources, an absence of consideration for the interrelationship between urban and rural areas and a weak role in context of local demands (Bogumil, 2019; Gnest, 2008; Pehlke et al., 2021; Spiekermann & Franck, 2014). These matters are of particular concern in Weser-Ems due to its lack of regional planning cooperations in comparison to other regions in Lower Saxony (Heuer et al., 2024). Existing shortcomings have resulted in sectoral planning directing attention towards seeking solutions at the state level. Ultimately, regional planning in Lower Saxony is more dependant on municipal and state planning level than vice versa (Bogumil et al., 2018; Gnest, 2008).

Regional planning and the socio-ecological transformation

Spatial planning is thought to have a particular role to play in enforcing the socio-ecological transformation, as it possesses the requisite tools to coordinate targets, strategies and development impulses between the different governance levels (Warner et al., 2021). As an intermediate level, regional planning plays a central role in adapting overarching policy objectives to regional circumstances and translating them into binding planning rules. Because of its cross-local perspective, regional planning is particularly important for minimising land take, the energy and mobility transition, and achieving equivalence of living conditions (Hahn et al., 2022).

Determining a “transformative” regional planning approach

The actual role of regional planning in transformation is still open for debate. A good introduction to the aspects to consider is provided in Hofmeister et al. (2021). Levin-Keitel und Behrend (2022) offer a comprehensive overview of the fundamental aspects of prevailing planning theories and their respective paradigms, thereby establishing a substantial theoretical foundation for the advancement of planning theory. In the context of regional planning practices in Germany, there is a diverse body of literature addressing the implementation of approaches that are more transformation-oriented. Examples of relevant publications include works by Brockhagen et al. (2023), Hahn et al. (2022), Malburg-Graf et al. (2024), and Kirchberg & Wilske (2023).

Determining the role of regional planning in transformation is very much dependent on the spatial context and comprehension of planning in general (Purkarthofer, 2020). The comprehension of planning has evolved over the last century. Its evolution is often associated with four “big turns” in terms of communication, strategy, culture and argumentation. These turns diversified practices without fully abolishing practices that preceded them (Levin-Keitel & Behrend, 2022; Othengrafen & Levin-Keitel, 2019; Wiechmann, 2019b). A new, more proactive, approach towards transformation therefore has to build upon contemporary practices and must consider the underlying planning cultures, as well as institution- and governance-related influences (Fürst, 2016; Gailing & Hamedinger, 2019; Othengrafen & Levin-Keitel, 2019; Purkarthofer & Stead, 2023; Schmitt & Wiechmann, 2018). “Transformative” planning is expected to go beyond the mere normative implementation of transformation requirements, which reflects only the content perspective. Equally important are the context, understood as the institutional constellation that provides space for innovation, and the process dimension, which focuses on fostering pluralistic will-formation (Bauriedl et al., 2021; Wiechmann, 2019a).

This comprehension encompasses the delineation of the function of planning within society and its legitimacy in interrelation with politics (Levin-Keitel and Behrend, 2022).

Struggles of regional planning with transformative innovation

Regional planning practice is still struggling to release its potential in terms of the socio-ecological transformation (Hofmeister & Warner, 2021; Lamker & Levin-Keitel, 2019; Heuer, Schäfer, & Schaal, 2024). Difficulties in harnessing its potential are typically linked to the ongoing societal discourse regarding actual action and unclear directives (Bauriedl et al., 2021). Yet, some of the difficulties are more deeply rooted in the characteristics of planning.

A fundamental conflict exists between the pursuit of flexibility and innovation on the one hand and the desire for commitment and consensus on the other (Fürst & Knieling, 2004). Transformation in general, and the socio-ecological transformation in particular, requires a high degree of innovation as well as societal consensus regarding its implementation (WBGU, 2011). However, innovation is contingent upon the existence of a plurality of opinions, an openness to new approaches and a willingness to engage in experimentation. Conversely, consensus, particularly that which is established through plans and concepts, necessitates a substantial degree of commitment, continuity and agreement on solutions (Fürst and Knieling, 2004; Malburg-Graf et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the increasing dynamism and impact of human activities and the related uncertainty render long-term planning more challenging (Birkmann et al., 2011; Capano et al., 2022; Lamker, 2016; McNeill, 2016). The socio-ecological transformation can be conceptualised as the organisation of the unplannable, necessitating its realisation within a narrow time frame (WBGU, 2011). The necessity for acceleration in planning is in tension with the risk of compromising the quality of the planning process (Sommer, 2024). The traditional critique of comprehensive planning, which asserts that it is too slow, too technical and too ineffective, is upheld and serves to impede action (Buße von Colbe et al., 2024; Danielzyk, 2004).

In contrast, politicians tend to favour sectoral solutions for acceleration (Hofmeister & Kanning, 2021). Recent examples in Germany are the act to accelerate the use of liquefied natural gas (LNGG) (Kment & Fimpel, 2022), the principle of “overriding interest” for renewable energy (§ 2 EEG) (Riese & Brennecke, 2021) and the temporarily used, but discontinued, “accelerated procedure” for land-use plans for housing (§13b BauGB) (Knieling et al., 2021). These solutions are characterised by a prioritisation of sectoral requirements that counteract objectives of holistic solutions and undermine fair assessment, communicative processes and environmental concerns (Kment & Fimpel, 2022; Knieling et al., 2021; Grotefels und Priebes 2024).

How to approach a more transformation-fit regional planning

The fundamental premise of LPP posits that within a system, a multitude of intervention options exist (Fischer et al., 2022). Within planning literature, a substantial number of intervention levers can be identified that have the potential to be employed for the purpose of transformative regional planning practice (Table 2). The subsequent synopsis is not intended to be exhaustive; its primary function is to demonstrate the diversity of known leverage points.

Table 2 - Examples of leverages in the context of regional planning (own depiction based on Meadows (1999)).

Leverage point	Leverage in planning context
1. Transcending paradigms	e.g. a societal paradigm shift towards a “proactive state” (WBGU, 2011)
2. Paradigms	e.g. a new planning understanding such as “turn to action” (Lamker & Levin-Keitel, 2019)
3. Goals	e.g. interpreting sustainable spatial development as a design mandate for transformation (Hofmeister & Kanning, 2021)
4. Self-organisation	e.g. strengthening the regional level (vertical power shift) (Harteisen et al., 2021).
5. Rules	e.g. clarifying legal norms (Schulz & Warner, 2021)
6. Information flows	e.g. strengthening data availability, accessibility and interoperability (Adams, 2020; Krause et al., 2020)
7. Reinforcing feedback loops	e.g. a more integrated usage of different planning tools (Harteisen et al., 2021)
8. Balancing feedback loops	e.g. fixing counteracting financial incentives (Burger & Bretschneider, 2022; Warner et al., 2021)
9. Delays	e.g. better aligning planning cycles with innovation cycles (Fürst & Knieling, 2004)
10. Stock and flow structures	e.g. adopting the structures to allow new planning roles (Othengrafen & Levin-Keitel, 2019; Warner et al., 2021)
11. Buffers	e.g. equipping planners with adequate funding for transformation (Warner et al., 2021)
12. Numbers	e.g. setting clear measures, timelines and responsibilities (Schulz & Warner, 2021)

The shallow leverages of transformative regional planning are those relating to practical implementation (see Table 2, Leverage 10-12). The actual leverage depends on the prevailing implementation context. The generalisability of these leverages constitutes a fundamental orientation of administrative action towards socio-ecological transformation. To this end, it is imperative to clearly delineate the measures, timelines, and responsibilities for transformative actions (Schulz & Warner, 2021). The emphasis must be placed on the underlying causative factors rather than on the manifestations of the problems (Malburg-Graf et al., 2024). The internal

structures of planning authorities must be dedicated to the overall aim of transformation, adequate funding must be provided to key actors and plans and concepts must be adopted towards transformation needs (Spiekermann & Franck, 2014; Warner et al., 2021).

A more fundamental approach concerns the influence and impact of regional planning, in particular with regard to its instruments (see Table 2, Leverage 7-9). A more integrated approach, combining strategic preparation, regional guidance, and implementation-oriented funding, is regarded as beneficial (Fürst et al., 2011; Harteisen et al., 2021; Kühn, 2008). Furthermore, financial and fiscal incentives should be utilised to support spatial planning objectives (Malburg-Graf et al., 2024) and incentives that currently encourage activities resulting in increased traffic or land take should be abolished (Burger & Bretschneider, 2022; Knieling et al., 2021; Warner et al., 2021). In terms of the temporal dimensions of feedback loops, it is of particular concern to better align planning cycles with innovation cycles (Fürst & Knieling, 2004; Herweg, 2015; Roggema et al., 2012).

The potential of system design is even more profound (see Table 2, Leverage 4-6). These leverages pertain to the power structures and competences of regional planning. Specifically, an enhancement of regional planning competences could be beneficial to better address the increasing number of supra-local challenges (Brockhagen et al., 2023; Harteisen et al., 2021; Hofmeister and Kanning, 2021). A further potential power shift could be a vertical one, which would strengthen regional planning in relation to economic development and support a more planning-oriented regional development (Harteisen et al., 2021; Hofmeister and Kanning, 2021).

The deepest leverages for enhancing regional planning can be identified in the system's overarching objectives (see Table 2, Leverage 1-3). It appears essential to reconsider the societal comprehension of planning. At present, the concept of a growth-oriented neoliberal enabling state, characterised by a significant reduction in state intervention, remains a dominant perspective (Fürst & Mäding, 2011; Kersten, 2022; Lamker, 2024). Conversely, the concept of a proactive state necessitates increased intervention to facilitate the socio-ecological transformation (WBGU, 2011). The practical implementation of such an understanding could entail a more active design approach (Harteisen et al., 2021; Lamker & Levin-Keitel, 2019).

Results: Determining leverage points for regional planning practice in Weser-Ems

The case study revealed a multitude of systemic challenges and leverages pertaining to regional planning within Weser-Ems (see Table 3). The most significant issues pertain to capacity constraints (11. Buffers), weak societal mandate for planning solutions (1. Transcending paradigms), inconsistent application of tools (12. Numbers/7. Reinforcing feedback loops) and the organisational structures (4. Self-organisation). The most significant leverages have been

identified as strengthening the role of regional planning in society (1. Transcending paradigms), sharpening the planning profile (2. Paradigms) and resolving open discussions on decision-making powers (4. Self-organisation).

Table 3 - Leverage points in the Weser-Ems region (own depiction; key results in **bold**).

Leverage point	Challenges	Leverage
1. Transcending paradigms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • weak societal mandate for planning solutions • dependence on local political dynamics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strengthen the public perception of planning • increased engagement in societal debates
2. Paradigms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • retreat to core tasks • prioritisation of straightforward solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sharpening of the planning profile • redefined role emphasising strategic, communicative and informal planning processes
3. Goals	[none identified]	[none identified]
4. Self-organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • narrow regional authority • neglect of the urban-rural nexus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sortition-based Citizens' Assembly
5. Rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • superficial participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • revision of citizen participation
6. Information flows	[none identified]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improved communication of the added value of planning • enhanced expectation management in participatory processes
7. Reinforcing feedback loops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inconsistent application of tools due to capacity constraints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • streamlining of available tools
8. Balancing feedback loops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prevalence of economic interests in regional development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • application of strategic visions in planning processes
9. Delays	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • obsolescence of plans • extended preparation timelines • insufficient adaptation to faster-paced state-level planning • need for acceleration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • emphasising a lean regional plan
10. Stock and flow structures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • single-person offices • lack of management functions 	[none identified]
11. Buffers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • capacity constraints • shortage of skilled labour • shortage of planning providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sharpening of the planning profile
12. Numbers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • limited influence on transformation issues • absence of integrated approaches • neglect of broader concerns in favour of energy transition priorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • emphasising a lean regional plan • application of strategic visions

Challenges

Capacity constraints (11. Buffers)

The constraints due to lack of financial and personnel capacities were evident in all results of the case study and were seen as the most significant challenge faced by regional planners in the questionnaire. During the workshop, capacity constraints were described in the form of a lack of personnel, skilled labour, financial resources and service providers. The survey of planning structures revealed that three of the counties only dedicated one position on regional planning, while county-free cities did not dedicate a specific position for regional planning at all. One of the counties reported that both regional planning positions are vacant. The participants of the workshop described the necessity to prioritise the implementation of feasible processes that are unlikely to be disrupted. Therefore, optimised communication, consensus-building and ambitious transformation ideas are given lower priority (2. Paradigms). The scarcity of funding was attributed to the limited political and social interest in regional planning solutions (1. Transcending paradigms).

Weak societal mandate for planning solutions (1. Transcending paradigms)

The second most significant issue identified was a weak societal mandate for regional planning solutions (1. Transcending paradigms). During the workshop, it became evident that planners do not perceive themselves to have a mandate to assume a more proactive role in the process of transformation. Stronger transformative impulses were perceived as a political responsibility. Participants have expressed discontent with the lack of explicit directives from a superior authority regarding the assumption of a strong mandate, as well as the lack of local-level support for a robust mandate.

Issues of utilising the toolbox (7. Reinforcing feedback loops)

The workshop revealed that the toolbox was perceived as sufficient, but capacity constraints limited its effective utilisation. Practical problems concern the regional plan. The document analysis revealed that regional plans are outdated (with a median age of 17 years), their preparation periods are taking very long (with a median time of 7 years) and that regional plans are not regularly adopted to updates to the state regional plan (9. Delays). The content of the plans revealed a deficiency in settlement development regulations and an absence of approaches to integrate regulations with funding or other implementation-oriented measures (12. Numbers/7. Reinforcing feedback loops). The survey questions revealed that the regional plans are perceived to have a poor cost-benefit ratio and being considered the most elaborate in comparison to other tools. Similarly critical attention concerned the preparatory land use plan

which was perceived as not fulfilling their intended task of depicting the long-term planning perspective of the municipalities.

Avoiding discussion of controversial structures (4. Self-organisation)

The findings of the case study substantiate the criticisms regarding the organisational structures of the municipalised regional planning in Lower Saxony. The resulting limited powers of regional planning authorities and the difficulties in delimiting their own room for manoeuvre and autonomy became evident. The issues were subjected to critical scrutiny during the workshop, yet the controversial nature of the topic precluded any debate on potential solutions. The subjects of power and competences were regarded as being too politically sensitive to propose any viable solutions.

Leverages

Strengthening the role of regional planning in society (1. Transcending paradigms)

Strengthening the role of regional planning in society was seen as a key leverage. A stronger communication emphasis should be dedicated to planning needs, benefits of planning processes and the expectation management in participation processes. Regional planners should communicate their insights on the interrelated sectoral impacts and needs for action more actively by engaging in socio-political discourses. In order to appeal to a wider audience, planning contents should be communicated in a more accessible and visual manner (6. Information flows/12. Numbers). The use of strong spatial imaginaries, such as the “green belt” in London or the “finger plan” in Copenhagen, was regarded as a means to make planning ideas more vivid. Another necessity is to introduce a more concise expectation management in participation processes. The workshop participants suggested the utilisation of drawn citizens assemblies and digital tools, such as PP-GIS, as means to bridge the gap of participation between the need to legitimise planning decisions by the administration and the call for active involvement by the public (4. Self-organisation/6. Information flows).

Sharpening the profile of regional planning (2. Paradigms)

A key outcome was the need to establish a clear profile of regional planning in Weser-Ems. This profile should consider what regional planning could ideally offer to society and what it pragmatically can provide. The workshop participants concluded that a holistic view and the fair weighting of interests should serve as the primary guiding principles. The key tasks were determined to be the management of land use, nature and landscape protection, and the allocation of energy infrastructure. It was suggested to establish a more informal planning

approach acting more communicatively, digitally, agile and strategically. Current practices should be streamlined to allow resources to be redistributed and aligned with these principals, tasks and practices (11. Buffers/7. Reinforcing feedback loops).

Clarifying decision making power (4. Self-organisation)

An important leverage was seen in the clarification of decision-making powers. The key challenges are seen in linking top-down and bottom-up approaches. Both approaches have their strengths and weaknesses. For regional planners, clear framework conditions are important in order to be able to assume a mandate for action. A clear mandate could be derived from top-down approaches, such as the WindBG Act⁶ issued in 2022 (WindBG, 2022). This parametric governance approach was perceived as a reinforcement of the mandate for regional planners (3. Goals/1. Transcending paradigms) as well as a practical challenge (12. Numbers). Conversely, direct-democratic elements (e.g. drawn citizens' assemblies) were discussed as means that could facilitate bottom-up ideas and gain support for their regional implementation. However, ideas of direct democracy were feared to compete with the decision-making processes of representative democracy (1. Transcending paradigms). The issue of reducing land consumption illustrated the limitations of both approaches. Municipalities and counties were seen as too dependent on growth-orientated local politics to provide satisfactory solutions from bottom-up. The state level, on the other hand, is considered too far away to be able to offer practicable solutions, as the demand for land take develops very varied and dynamically at local level. Parametric targets could hardly do adequate justice to the actual development.

Discussion: Intervention strategies for Weser-Ems

A continuation of the status quo of regional planning practices in Weser-Ems is not a feasible option. In light of the mounting challenges and unaltered financial resources, an intensifying retreat to core formal tasks seems without alternative (cf. Hoffmann & Schönwald, 2023; Lamker, 2016; Othengrafen & Levin-Keitel, 2019). This retreat would result in a greater number of topics and decisions-making powers being transferred to other levels of planning and sectoral approaches, as can be observed both in the past (Gnest, 2008) and today (Priebes, 2022). The role of regional planning would devolve into an administrative distribution task devoid of conceptual autonomy and a mere conduit for transformative issues. Potential risks associated with this involuntary retreat are that comprehensive considerations, communication of planning

⁶ The WindBG is a federal act that clearly defines targets for the areas designated for the expansion of wind energy (WindBG, 2022).

objectives and even regional development could become less prominent (Grotefels & Priebes, 2024; Othengrafen & Levin-Keitel, 2019).

A paradigm shift towards a more informal, communicative planning seems to be a feasible orientation for reformation. The use of LPP has shown that the leverage for this paradigm shift lays rather in the adaptation of the other leverages towards this new paradigm than in convincing regional planners about this paradigm. Intervention needs and theoretical solutions seem well known among regional planners but the leverage points to solve these issues are strongly related to external factors. These issues cannot be solved solely by the regional planners but need a more structural approach.

Engaging society, enabling change

The prevailing critical view regarding regional solutions in Lower Saxony (Fürst, 1987; Gnest, 2008) can be confirmed and is resulting in a missing baseline to enforce a strong mandate for transformative impulses by regional planners. A well-known leverage point to address this issue is to improve the weak social embedment by improved communication (cf. Fürst, 1987; Knieling et al., 2021; Priebes, 1998). Regional planners should improve their argumentative power (Zimmermann, 2019), present themselves as supportive and facilitative partners in the region (cf. Danielzyk & Knieling, 2011) and engage in social debates as spatial experts stressing the benefits of holistic solutions (cf. Levin-Keitel and Behrend, 2022; Hahn et al., 2022). This communicative approach has its supporters in literature (cf. Danielzyk & Knieling, 2011; Danielzyk & Sondermann 2019; Fürst, 2012; Fürst et al., 2011; Harteisen et al., 2021; Healey, 1992; Hutter et al., 2019; Kühn, 2008; Lamker, 2016; Sondermann & Maikämper, 2024; Vallée, 2012; Zimmermann, 2019) and has been emphasised by other states, for example North Rhine Westphalia (Brockhagen et al., 2023).

Obstacles

The case study revealed that regional planners in Weser-Ems are lacking the robust foundation for implementation of this approach. Concerns have been voiced that they are not receiving sufficient support from local authorities to engage in activities that extend beyond clearly defined legal mandates. Furthermore, capacity constraints limit possibilities to engage in voluntary activities.

Leverage points

A strong mandate for informal practices and active implementation of transformation can be demanded more strongly by regional planners. They can refer to

- 1) the legal obligation to serve the common good and to aim for sustainable spatial development (§1 (2) ROG) (cf. Harteisen et al., 2021),
- 2) the need for comprehensive and consistent actions in view of the climate and biodiversity crises (cf. Levin-Keitel and Behrend, 2022),
- 3) and the robust scientific basis that illustrates the needs and benefits of communicative planning on regional level (Sondermann & Maikämper, 2024).

Regional planners will be required to gain a political self-consciousness of active involvement as well as a better understanding of political processes and the values and intentions that underlie them (Sondermann & Maikämper, 2024). They should adapt their language to the understanding of politicians (cf. Hahn et al., 2022) and should require the negotiation skills to advocate for their topics (cf. Levin-Keitel and Behrend, 2022). They will require support by political stakeholders for this. Political stakeholders should acknowledge that regional planning is a comprehensive tool to actively shape transformation and thus gain interest in its transformative application (cf. Hahn et al., 2022).

Redefining roles, refocusing resources

A strategy that could support a new planning role is a redistribution of planning means. Currently a mismatch between expectations and actual resources exists and improvements in terms of funding are not expected by the queried stakeholders. A redistribution of means and a redefinition of tasks and obligations is therefore a key aspect of reshaping the profile of regional planning. This will require a streamlining of mandatory formal tasks in order to adjust planning activities to a more active design approach.

Obstacles

Streamlining mandatory formal tasks carries the inherent risk of butterfly effects, which may result in less effective powers to counteract negative developments. This is evidenced by the experiences of the liberalisation of planning in the Netherlands and Denmark which have resulted in a significant deterioration in the capacity of regional planning to address the adverse impacts of uneven development and land consumption (Galland, 2012; Nadin et al., 2021; Waterhout et al., 2013). Another obstacle of streamlining mandatory formal tasks is the fact that the German planning system generally appears very slow to adapt in comparison to other European countries. Its inertia, rooted in the idea of security, protects it from rash actions and loss of control, but deems streamlining more difficult (Galland, 2012; Münter & Reimer, 2023; Nadin et al., 2021; Waterhout et al., 2013).

Leverage points

A cautious streamlining that ensures that the integrated view, the weighing up of interests and the protective functions are not compromised, was regarded as a viable solution for Weser-Ems. Both regional plans and preparatory land-use plans were identified as tools in need of revision. Examples for streamlining are a lean regional plan (Fürst & Peithmann, 1999) and the merging of parallel planning documents (“one space – one plan”) (Peithmann, 2008). Both ideas refer to concentrating existing means on key tasks of regional planning and to paying less attention to issues that are already regulated by other planning levels or sectoral planning. Parallel planning and unnecessary confirmation loops could be avoided by focusing on the specific issues and competencies of each planning level. An illustrative example are the Natura 2000 areas, which are clearly defined areas protected by EU law. Nevertheless, they must be confirmed in all plans from state to municipal level. Other determinations, such as the extraction of raw materials, are determined at state level on the basis of area-specific data and are nevertheless re-evaluated on the basis of the same data at regional level. In particular, regional plans and preparatory land-use plans bear numerous mandatory tasks in common. Given the proximity of the scale level, these tasks are unlikely to result in any substantial differences in the assessment process. Consequently, a mandatory double assessment is often redundant in many cases (Fürst & Peithmann, 1999; Peithmann, 2008). The deficits in the use of the regional plan and the preparatory land-use plan recognised in the case study underline the need for further consideration of merging these plans (Sondermann & Maikämper, 2024).

Enabling cooperation, evolving structures

Since its introduction, municipalised regional planning in Lower Saxony has been the subject of debate in terms of its sufficiency (Bogumil et al., 2018; Fürst, 1987; Gnest, 2008; Spiekermann & Franck, 2014). The case study emphasises that the related capacity constraints and the weak power restrict the potential roles that can be assumed and the instruments that can be employed. This structural weakness constrains the scope of planning activities regardless of the specific objective and has an impact on all levels of intervention to a certain extent.

Obstacles

The challenge in addressing the structural issues is that the German planning system is very persistent (Münter & Reimer, 2023) and the existing structures are deeply embedded in the cultural fabric of Lower Saxony (cf. Gnest, 2008). Furthermore, structural reforms are politically sensitive (Bogumil & Ebinger, 2019; Krüger & Müller, 2018; Tautz et al., 2018) with associated risks of discontent, populism and low voter turnout (Blesse & Rösel, 2017). The inaccessibility of

specific leverages (Fischer et al., 2022) is particularly evident in this context. Even ideas of intervention detours were deemed critically in the workshop discussions.

Leverage points

A variety of intervention detours to reform the overall regional planning structures in the Weser-Ems exist. For instance, it is feasible to transfer the responsibility of regional planning to a special-purpose association (§20 (2) NROG). Indeed, § 5(4) NROG explicitly calls for the establishment of collaborative arrangements for the metropolitan areas of major cities (NROG, 2024). The “Regionalverband Großraum Braunschweig” and the “Region Hannover” showcase the benefits as well as the prerequisites for such forms of cooperation. These kinds of collaborations are the result of lengthy processes that facilitate the establishment of trust between the partners (Bogumil and Grohs, 2010; Fürst, 1999; Priebes, 1997, 2010). Less formalised, low-threshold cooperation represents a necessary step on the way to establishing such co-operations (Bogumil and Grohs, 2010). Weser-Ems is currently even lacking good examples of low-threshold cooperation that could serve as a foundation for more formalised forms of collaboration. Thus, the first step should be to focus on initiating and expanding cooperation with a holistic spatial perspective by identifying common challenges and channelling existing informal exchanges.

Conclusion: Systemic constraints and leverage points in regional planning: Lessons from Weser-Ems

The case study confirms persistent structural deficiencies in the implementation of regional planning in Weser-Ems. It emphasises that both core tasks and transformative practices are being negatively influenced. In view of the increasing challenges of transformation, the need for reformation is becoming ever more apparent. A variety of prominent reform ideas have thus far proven unappealing or unfeasible. The underlying factors that have contributed to their failure have been identified as a deficiency in resources and an absence of socio-political support. A systematic approach is therefore imperative.

The LPP has permitted a feasible systematic analysis of potential intervention strategies for the purpose of enhancing the practice of regional planning in Weser-Ems. The LPP facilitated a discussion on the interrelationships between adaptation requirements, solutions and opportunities in combination. This facilitated the discussion of the solutions in a contextualised manner, with an emphasis on their acceptance and feasibility. The key leverage points were defined as follows: 1) the social basis was to be strengthened by more active engagement; 2) the

role was to be redefined by refocussing priorities; and 3) structures were to be adapted by emphasising cooperation.

It is evident that these leverages are highly dependent on external factors. Consequently, the subsequent steps will necessitate a greater emphasis on stakeholders outside of regional planning. A diverse range of stakeholders must be brought together and commit to resolving their conflicting demands. The LPP could assist by presenting the leverages and their interconnections in a concise and accessible manner. The transdisciplinary process required for this extends beyond the scope of this case study and has yet to be initiated. The discrepancy between expectations and capabilities must be resolved, and a precise mandate must be established. This will necessitate socio-political decisions regarding pivotal aspects of governance and transformation. The aforementioned steps encompass 1) the distribution of decision-making authority (top-down vs. bottom-up, as well as representative vs. direct democracy), 2) the modalities of enforcement (prohibitions vs. incentives) and 3) the pace of implementation (acceleration vs. caution). It is imperative that a feasible solution is formulated, with the objective of aligning responsibilities, powers and structures.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares that he has no conflict of interest.

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